

Effectiveness of combined therapy: (Intralesional injections and topical interferon) in treatment of ocular surface squamous neoplasia (OSSN)

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Ocular surface squamous neoplasia (OSSN) is considered as most frequent non-pigmented neoplasm for ocular surface. It initiates from corneal or conjunctiva epithelium. Many chemotherapeutic and immunotherapeutic agents have been suggested in place of surgery. This includes interferon. **Objective:** The present study is aimed to assess effectiveness of combined therapy in treating ocular surface squamous neoplasia. **Methodology:** For this purpose, a retrospective study was conducted that included 72 patients having OSSN. The patients had age range of 18 to 80 years. The patients were either given topical, intralesional or combined therapy of interferon. The demographic characteristics were noted for each patient after collecting informed consent. A follow up of 6 months was given. **Results:** The mean age of included patients was 60 ± 15 years. The OSSN was more prominent in male gender and right eye. Majority of the cases had no identifiable risk factor. The interferon showed a clinical resolution within 0.5 to 9 months, being apparent in majority (86.1 %) patients. **Conclusion:** The use of interferon is highly recommended with success rate of 86.1%, low recurrence rate (3 cases) and no adverse effects.

Keywords : combined therapy, ocular surface squamous neoplasia

INTRODUCTION

Ocular surface squamous neoplasia (OSSN) is considered as most frequent non-pigmented neoplasm of ocular surface that starts from limbus, conjunctival or corneal epithelium (Shields et al. 2004). However, some variants of pigmented types also exist in African regions. Lee and Hirst proposed the term 'ocular surface squamous neoplasia', which comprises of carcinomatous and dysplastic lesions of ocular surface. The OSSN is usually localized within the interpalpebral fissure, in correspondence to regions of sun exposure. It is slow in growth due to which it rarely assaults orbit, sinuses or globe. The lesions can have impact on complete thickness of epithelium (Mata et al. 2014). It can also surpass the basement membrane and assault stroma. The etiology of OSSN includes human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), allergy, exposure to Ultraviolet B radiation, intense smoking, environmental factors, genetic factors, exposure to petroleum products and human

papillomavirus (HPV) 16 and 18 (Karp et al. 2010). The HPV has highly been found in OSSN samples as compared to healthy conjunctiva. However, the detection frequencies vary in accordance to countries. The ability of E6 and E7 oncoproteins to target, intermingle and degrade host proteins is responsible for HPV based carcinogenesis. Moreover, the immuno-comprised individuals the ability to recognize tumor by immune cells is suppressed, due to which they are more likely to suffer from OSSN (Moon et al. 2016). In cutaneous malignancies, DNA is damaged by UV and cancer promoting mutations are produced. The individuals do not have ability to repair DNA mutations due to which they have high risk of UV-induced cell damage. Consequently, they are highly prone to ocular surface and cutaneous malignancies (Scott, Karp & Nuovo 2002).

The incidence of OSSN varies geographically, with lower incidence in areas with less sun exposure. The estimated incidence of OSSN ranges from 0.13 to 1.9 persons per 100,000 individuals (Boehm & Huang 2004). Usually OSSN takes place in 6th decade of life; however, it can also exist in youngsters if affiliated with human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) or xerodermapigmentosum (XP). Previous research works have shown high incidence of OSSN in HIV patients. It has also been found that OSSN pathology is more aggressive in African American people as compared to western ones (Sturges, Butt & Lai 2008).

A wide variety of treatment options are present in literature for OSSN. The most accepted one among these techniques is the surgical excision with 'no touch' method. Anyhow, it has high recurrence rates including 33% with negative surgical borders and 56% with positive surgical borders (Karp et al. 2010). Resultantly, adjuvant agents have been proposed. This includes chemotherapeutic agents like 5-fluorouracil and mitomycin C, immunotherapy agents like interferon alpha-2b and antiviral agents like cidofovir (Poothullil & Colby, 2006). These substances are included under non-invasive technique to treat conjunctiva. This method is affiliated with least side effects and helps

to attain high concentrations that can be changed in accordance with the clinical response (de la Cruz et al. 2014).

Interferon alpha-2b (IFN α -2b) is a glycoprotein in nature. It is produced against viral infections by leukocytes. It consists of antineoplastic, antimicrobial and antiviral activities due to cytotoxic, antiangiogenic and antiproliferative effects (Bracarda, Eggermont & Samuelsson 2010). It can increase cytotoxic and phagocytic mechanism, decrease blood vessel proliferation, hinder biosynthetic enzymes, initiate apoptosis and inhibit viral RNA. The mechanism of antitumor effect of interferon is both direct and indirect in nature. The cytostatic effect of interferon enhances cell cycle time in tumor cells, which results in metabolites depletion and growth slowdown of tumor (Fernandes et al. 2014). Moreover, it initiates apoptosis, prohibits biosynthetic enzymes, initiates antibodies production against tumor cells, tumor cytotoxicity through immune response and initiates expression of cell surface antigens (Galor, et al., 2015). Interferon has less side effects and better tolerance than other agents. It can be used for treating OSSN through topical, subconjunctival and perilesional injection routes (Schechter, Koreishi & Karp 2008).

Interferon is mainly a cytokine consisting of 165 amino acids having immunodulatory effects. In intralesional therapy of interferon, production of interleukin 2 and IFN- γ mRNA are increased by immune system, whereas, the generation of interleukin 10 is reduced. This help in targeting and identification of neoplastic cells (Nanji et al. 2014). Interferon can be used as subconjunctival injections, topical eye drops or combination of both for treating OSSN. These therapies can be used as primary as well as adjuvant therapies (Galor, Karp, & Chhabra, Topical interferon alpha 2b eye-drops for treatment of ocular surface squamous neoplasia: a dose comparison study, 2010).

In topical therapy, interferon dose is usually 1 million IU/ml, which is administered four times a day for about two months following lesion resolution. However, doses of 2 and 3 million IU/ml have also been reported. The clinical resolution of lesions takes place usually within 4 months of treatment. Previous research works have also claimed that the efficacy between 1 and 3 million IU/ml doses is same with no difference in treatment duration and clinical resolution (Bracarda, Eggermont & Samuelsson 2010). The topical therapy has benefit of ease in use with least adverse effects. The intralesional injections have been affiliated with more side effects such as flu-

like symptoms. However, the injections have advantage of being cost-effective as medication is mostly covered by insurers. It also has assured compliance, better resolution and the need of compounding is not present (Kamal et al. 2015).

Although topical therapy of interferon have almost negligible side effects, some studies have notified follicular conjunctivitis, formation of epithelial microcysts and hyperemia to occur as a result of therapy. Intralesional injections mostly results in flu-like symptoms that may exist for 46h after application of injection. To deal with this side effect, 1g of oral acetaminophen is given with injection and when required until symptoms come to an end (Mata et al. 2014).

Many research works have emphasized on the use of topical interferon therapy as mono and primary treatment method for OSSN (Moon et al. 2016). However, the need for refrigeration and high costs of compounding makes use of topical therapy of interferon less applicable. In some countries it may be inexpensive, but in majority of countries they are not affordable. On the other hand, intralesional injections are usually covered by insurers and commercially available, which removes the requirement of compounding (Karp et al. 2010). The aim of present study is to assess efficiency of combined therapy (Intralesional injections and topical interferon) in treating ocular surface squamous neoplasia (OSSN)

METHODOLOGY

The present study was a non-randomized and retrospective in nature, performed at THQ Hospital, Muridky, Sheikhpura. It included data of patients with diagnosis of ocular surface squamous neoplasia (OSSN) from January 2018 to January 2019. The data of the patients were search and included from files of hospital. The patients with age range 18 to 80 were included. The informed consents from patients were collected. All of the participants showed their willingness to be treated with interferon or combined therapy. This may also include photographic control and follow up of six months. The demographic variables, type of therapy, time of follow up, time of treatment, relapse and associated complications were noted for each patient.

Type of therapy

1. Topical therapy: The concentration used for interferon was 1 million international units in 1 ml, which was given as one drop at time interval of 6 hours for 1 month following clinical decree of disease.

2. Intralesional therapy: The concentration of 3 million international units of interferon in 0.5ml was given once in a week until decrease of disease.
3. Combined therapy: The topical and intralesional therapy were combined.

The follow-up was given monthly for first three months after decrease of disease, followed by three months intervals and finally bi-annual follow-up was given for each patient.

RESULTS

Total of 72 individuals were found with treatment of interferon. The mean age for included patients was 60 ± 15 years ranging from 18 to 80 years, as shown in the Table 1. The male gender was found to be more prone towards OSSN with 52 (72.22%) cases. The right eye was found to be more affected one with 40 (55.55%) cases. Majority of the cases (38.88%) were found with no associated risk factor. HIV was found in 13 (18.05%) cases, sun exposure was found in 11 (15.27%) cases, whereas, smoking and HPV were found in 10 (13.88%) cases as an associated risk factor.

Table 1: Demographics of patients

Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	60 ± 15 (18-80)	
Gender		
Male	52	72.22 %
Female	20	27.77 %
Eye		
Right	40	55.55 %
Left	32	44.44 %
Associated risk factors		
None	28	38.88 %
Smoking	10	13.88 %
Sun exposure	11	15.27 %
HIV	13	18.05 %
HPV	10	13.88 %

Three groups were formed as topical (n=24), intralesional (n=24) and combined therapy (n=24). The average time of treatment was higher in intralesional group (6.1 months) as compared to topical group (4.3 months), shown in Table 2. No postoperative complications or adverse effects were found in association with the treatment with interferon. In combined therapy group, no recurrence case was found, whereas, 2 (2.77%) cases were found in topical and 1 (1.38%) case was found in intralesional group. The interferon showed a clinical resolution within 0.5 to 9 months, being apparent in majority (86.1%) patients.

Table 2: Comparison of results for therapies

Treatment group	Topical (n=24)	Intralesional (n=24)	Combined (n=24)
Age (years)	59.2	61.1	60.2
Recurrences	2 (2.77%)	1 (1.38%)	0 (0 %)
Time of use (months)	4.3	6.1	4.4
Time of follow up (months)	16.5	16.3	16.6

DISCUSSION

The average age of OSSN patients in present study was 60 ± 15 years. The male gender showed predominance as compared to female gender. This is in accordance with the previous research work of Kamal et al (2015). Although majority (38.88%) of the cases were not associated with any risk factor, smoking, sun exposure, HIV and HPV history were found to be associated in 13.88%, 15.27%, 18.05% and 13.88% cases. The previous research works have extensively described these risk factors to be part of etiology of OSSN (Kamal et al 2015; Fernandes et al 2014; Karp et al 2010).

The usual treatment of OSSN includes surgical excision and cryotherapy. Though widely accepted, these therapies result in limbal stem cell deficiency along with astigmatism, symblepharon, and high rates of recurrences (Moon et al 2016; Karp et al 2010). According to Karp et al (2010), this type of treatment further perplexes in patients with large OSSN lesions at limbus or recurrent cases. Consequently, different chemotherapies have been employed including interferon. The preferred way of giving interferon therapy is through topical route as it eliminates injection application, which results in systemic side effects (Fernandes et al, 2014). Despite this advantage, the topical therapy of interferon needs longer duration for achieving

complete clinical resolution, which further requires medication cooling and patient cooperation. In such a scenario, combined therapy may act as a cost-effective treatment for large tumors that may help in achieving better penetration (Karp et al, 2010).

In present study, mean time for topical use of interferon was 4.3 months, which is similar to that described by works of Nanji et al (2014) and Karp et al (2010). Anyhow, the average time for intralesional therapy was higher than previous research works (Karp et al 2010). This can be due to non-randomized and retrospective nature of study, which results in elongation of topical treatment to tumors with higher dosage and treatment time.

According to studies of Boehm and Huang (2004) and Sturges et al (2008), the topical treatment with interferon is safe and well tolerated with no reported side effects in majority of cases. Anyhow, minor side effects such as follicular conjunctivitis and conjunctival hyperemia have been reported in work of Schechter et al (2008). In the present study, no side effect was reported for topical therapy with interferon. According to Fernandes et al (2014), adverse effects of topical therapy diminish with discontinuation of the treatment. In intralesional therapy with interferon, side effects such as myalgias, fever and flu like symptoms may appear. However, these side effects are found to be mild and well tolerated in nature by Karp et al (2010). In present study no deaths or carcinogenic side effects were reported for any therapy of interferon. This is in accordance with the study of Fernandes et al (2014).

REFERENCES

- Boehm, M & Huang, A 2004, 'Treatment of recurrent corneal and conjunctival intraepithelial neoplasia with topical interferon alfa 2b', *Ophthalmology*, vol 111, pp. 1755-61.
- Bracarda, S, Eggermont, A & Samuelsson, J 2010, 'Redefining the role of interferon in the treatment of malignant diseases', *Eur J Cancer*, vol 46, pp. 284-297.
- de la Cruz Aguiló, R, Duch-Samper, A, Hernández, PD & Marí, CJ 2014, 'Conjunctival intraepithelial neoplasia. Interferon as a rescue therapy after failure of mitomycin C', *Arch Soc Esp Oftalmol*, vol 89, no. 11, pp. 463-5.
- Fernandes, B, Nikolitch, K, Coates, J, Novais, G, Odashiro, A, Odashiro, P, Belfort, R & Burnier, M 2014, 'Local chemotherapeutic agents for the treatment of ocular malignancies', *Surv Ophthalmol*, vol 59, no. 1, pp. 97-114.
- Galor, A, Garg, N, Nanji, A, Joag, M, Nuovo, G, Palioura, S, Wang, G & Karp, C 2015, 'Human Papilloma Virus Infection Does Not Predict Response to Interferon Therapy in Ocular Surface Squamous Neoplasia', *Ophthalmology*, vol 122, no. 11, pp. 2210-5.
- Galor, A, Karp, C & Chhabra, S 2010, 'Topical interferon alpha 2b eye-drops for treatment of ocular surface squamous neoplasia: a dose comparison study', *Br J Ophthalmol*, vol 94, pp. 551-4.

In the topical interferon group, recurrence rate of 2.77% was observed, which is in accordance with the study of Nanji et al (2014), which claims modality range of 0% to 17 %. On the other hand, the recurrence rate for intralesional therapy was 1.38%. This is lower than the reported percentage of 3% in study of Nanji et al (2014). The follow-up time for topical and intralesional therapies were 16.5 and 16.3 months. The difference in recurrence rate may be influenced by number of patients and follow up time. In the combined therapy group, no recurrence case was found with follow-up of 16.6 months. The previous research works of Galor et al (2010), Nanji et al (2014), Galor et al (2015) and Karp et al (2010) supports this finding.

The present study was limited in terms of retrospective nature, due to which it may have selection biases. Thus, the future research works should focus on exploring and comparing these three techniques in a prospective way.

CONCLUSION

The interferon appears to be very effective in treating ocular surface squamous neoplasia. A success rate of 86.1% was achieved with low recurrence rate (3 patients). Moreover, no complications or adverse effects of the treatments were found in follow-up period. It is a potential substitute to traditional treatment as it is efficient in immune reduction of tumor. Moreover, it replaces surgical treatment and can act as a monotherapy as well.

- Kamal, S, Kaliki, S, Mishra, D, Batra, J & Naik, M 2015, 'Ocular Surface Squamous Neoplasia in 200 Patients: A Case-Control Study of Immunosuppression Resulting from Human Immunodeficiency Virus versus Immunocompetency', *Ophthalmology*, vol 122, no. 8, pp. 1688-94.
- Karp, C, Galor, A, Chhabra, S, Barnes, S & Alfonso, E 2010, 'Subconjunctival/perilesional recombinant interferon α 2b for ocular surface squamous neoplasia: a 10-year review', *Ophthalmology*, vol 117, no. 12, pp. 2241-6.
- Mata, E, Conesa, E, Castro, M, Martínez, L, de Pablo, C & González, M 2014, 'Carcinoma epidermoide conjuntival: respuesta paradójica al colirio interferón', *Arch Soc Esp Oftalmol*, vol 89, no. 7, pp. 293-6.
- Moon, C, Nanji, A, Galor, A, McCollister, K & Karp, C 2016, 'Surgical versus Medical Treatment of Ocular Surface Squamous Neoplasia: A Cost Comparison', *Ophthalmology*, vol 123, no. 3, pp. 497-504.
- Nanji, A, Moon, C, Galor, A, Sein, J, Oellers, P & Karp, C 2014, 'Surgical versus medical treatment of ocular surface squamous neoplasia: a comparison of recurrences and complications', *Ophthalmology*, vol 121, no. 5, pp. 994- 1000.
- Poothullil, A & Colby, K 2006, 'Topical medical therapies for ocular surface tumors', *Semin Ophthalmol*, vol 21, pp. 161–169.
- Schechter, B, Koreishi, A & Karp, C 2008, 'Longterm follow up of conjunctival and corneal intraepithelial neoplasia treated with topical interferon alfa-2b', *Ophthalmology*, vol 115, pp. 1291-6.
- Scott, I, Karp, C & Nuovo, G 2002, 'Human papillomavirus 16 and 18 expression in conjunctival intraepithelial neoplasia', *Ophthalmology*, vol 109, pp. 542–7.
- Shields, C, Demirci, H, Karatza, E & Shields, J 2004, 'Clinical survey of 1643 melanocytic and nonmelanocytic conjunctival tumors', *Ophthalmology*, vol 111, pp. 1747–54.
- Sturges, A, Butt, A & Lai, J 2008, 'Topical interferon or surgical excision for the management of primary ocular surface squamous neoplasia', *Ophthalmology*, vol 115, pp. 1297-302.